

The Importance of the Self-Healing Doctor

By Blake Pierpoint

Far too often do we hear the phrase “They had a whole life ahead of them” when referring to aspiring physicians who fell victim to the seemingly insurmountable demands of medical school. Suicide rates amongst medical students have grown increasingly over the years and medical schools are beginning to take notice. Mental health issues have become a crisis within medical schools, and it seems that nothing has been able to alleviate the situation. To lower depression rates, medical schools must begin implementing programs emphasizing the diagnosis and treatment of depression within their student body.

It’s a weight on your mind that you can’t bear. A lead cape you drag around with you through the halls. A thick fog that settles in the classroom, clouding your mind with negativity. Depression is an illness that utilizes one’s life situation as a catalyst for its psychological effects. Medical students can be considered as the most susceptible demographic to depression. High academic stress, sleepless nights and strained time increase the risk of developing depression. Medical students can also be considered the most helpless demographic to depression. The social stigma of depression within medical school results in medical students resisting treatment, as it could potentially deem them unfit for their job.

Stigma can be considered a primary contributor to the growing crisis of depression within medical school. Many medical students begin to experience a correlation between mental resilience and respect amongst their peers. Frequently linking their inability to handle academic stress with a lower social standing. Medical school requires frequent peer interaction and group work, resulting in strong bonds that carry significant emotional weight on students. Spending

hours studying with the same group of people on a daily basis begins to create tight knit bonds. Medical students find themselves greatly valuing the opinion of their peers, furthering the importance of peer acceptance in their eyes.

The impact of peer influence on medical students was shown in a survey taken by the University of Michigan Medical School, “Students with moderate to severe depression frequently agreed that ‘if I were depressed, fellow medical students would respect me less’” (Schwenck et al.). It’s clear that medical students feel the stigma around depression. Many choose to avoid running the risk of their depression becoming public. As “56 percent of depressed students suspect they would lose the respect of their colleagues if their depression became public” and “83 percent of depressed students suspect that faculty would view them as unfit for their responsibilities” (Koti). Medical students don’t feel comfortable seeking the treatment they need. Many medical students are forced to suppress their feelings out of fear of being deemed incapable of providing effective medical care. Medical students are forced to just deal with the negative outlook, it’s nothing more than a feeling, it isn’t real.

As inner tension rises from social acceptance, the pressures of academic achievement increasingly strain the mental wellbeing of medical students. It’s one thing to get into medical school, it’s another to excel while you’re there. For many medical students this challenge entails unrealistic ideals of academic excellence. Perfection becomes an expectation, and the stress of upholding these standards impacts the minds of many medical students. Academic competitiveness plays a major role in the stress-inducing atmosphere of medical school. The stigma surrounding depression prevents students from addressing their issues, while the academic competition worsens their symptoms. Much of a medical students time is spent group studying, where students work together to accomplish a unified understanding of course material.

A student who has prepared similarly to their peers and ends up scoring lower on an exam begins questioning their intellect. Once confidence begins wavering, and a student begins questioning themselves, their mental health suffers. Academic competition is healthy to some extent, in the case of medical students, it is just another stressor added to an already overwhelming list.

To understand the amount of academic pressure medical students experience we must quantify the time an average medical student spends studying. Ryan Nguyen, an osteopathic medical student, took the time to record his study sessions for a two-week period before an exam. He found that on average he spent 4.8 hours a day studying. Explaining that his first year in medical school felt like a college finals week, “stretched out over a 9-month period” (Nguyen, par 4). To put the coursework of medical students in perspective, Nguyen compared the quantity of information a medical student must retain to the quantity of information a college student must retain. Medical students are allocated 2 weeks to study 37 hours of lecture material. While college students usually have around 10 weeks to study 30 hours of lecture material (Nguyen, par 2). Time always seems to be strained for medical students, putting an immense amount of pressure on their mental health. Medical students spend so much time studying copious amounts of information that they begin to disregard their psychological well-being. Medical schools must begin emphasizing the importance of maintaining a healthy mental state, and being conscientious of one’s mood throughout each semester.

Time is always of the essence for a medical student. Wasting away even an hour of a day can have overwhelming consequences. Grades, mental and physical health all perform a waltz of alternating importance throughout medical school. Finding stability requires consistent monitoring of one’s time management skills. It seems medical students end up in a cyclical state of situational stress that seems inescapable. Medical students begin questioning their purpose in

medical school as a result of this constant extrinsic pressure. As Ken Saxton explained in a speech given to the 2010 freshman class at the University of California, “One of my friends in business school went through med school first, only to discover that he hated it” (438). Medical school is a commitment that not all are willing to make. The time needed to retain the chapters of information becomes far too daunting and many lose their passion for the medical field. For some, the medical school burnout leads to a change in career paths. For others, the burnout leads to feelings of helplessness and depression. Many medical students force themselves to stay in medical school, fearing that the shame and judgement of dropping out will be crippling. Choosing to continue their demanding, time-consuming lives as medical students further accentuates the pessimistic outlooks they have developed. Eventually, their negatively skewed perception of the world catches up, and depressive states become common. Medical schools must address medical school burnout, and begin implementing programs that focus on revitalizing the passion within their student body.

Implementing programs that provide anonymous and easily accessible treatment for medical students suffering from depression could be highly beneficial. An issue as complex as depression may have a very simple resolution. It’s established that medical students feel strong social stigma surrounding depression. Medical schools can address the issue surrounding stigma by prioritizing mental health issues within the culture of medicine. Programs that promote the open discussion of depression will raise awareness on the issue and encourage open-minded consideration for those who suffer from it. Changes have already been taking place to promote the normalization of mental health issues across medical schools. Policies have been put in place requiring medical schools to provide mental health services separate from the academic

environment. A combination of confidential treatment, and the normalization of mental health issues could result in significantly lower depression levels (Grossman 4).

Schools like Harvard, Duke and University of California San Francisco have all begun implementing mental health workshops. Students receive information on utilizing “mindfulness and self-renewing skills” that include tips on sleep habits and stress management. Other common programs involved “stress rounds” where students could share experiences and responses during their clinical rounds. Accessibility is another important factor to consider when implementing mental health programs. Providing free wellness services should become mandatory across all medical schools. Anonymity must also be required to provide a judgement free atmosphere for students utilizing the services (Rosenthal and Okie 1085).

The effects of negative mental health in medical school have long lasting effects on even the most well-established physicians. A medical student who suffered from depression is very likely to have regrets during their clinical careers. A doctor who has lost his passion is a doctor who puts all of his patients at risk, which frequently results in malpractice lawsuits. In Atul Gawande’s bestselling non-fiction book, “Complications: A Surgeons Notes on an Imperfect Science”, Gawande details the life of Hank Goodman, a world renowned orthopedic surgeon who began facing many malpractice lawsuits in the latter part of his career. Patients and fellow physicians began commenting on his change of demeanor. Eventually, Goodman ended up retiring in shame. Following many years in retirement, Goodman revealed he had lost his passion with medicine years before. His lack of interest can be attributed to his experience in medical school and residency. The long hours, restless nights and pestering thoughts resulted in major depressive disorder. After his clinical residency, he began questioning his purpose as a doctor. He realized the years he dedicated training was time he had wasted in constant stress and

negativity. The years of his youth were lost in an abyss of pessimism and the fire he once had for this career was put out. The only reason he chose to continue his clinical practice was in pursuit of more spending money. It's common to joke about one's "mid-life crisis", but when it applies to an emergency room physician, such a crisis puts countless lives at risk (Gawande).

We put our lives in the hands of doctors, trusting that they are knowledgeable enough to solve our physiological issues. Rarely do we consider how our doctors are doing themselves. A physician can only provide effective clinical care for their patients if they are caring for themselves. We see doctors as selfless and noble, sacrificing hours of their day to ensure the health of their respective communities. Medical schools attempt to produce doctors who exhibit selflessness and unwavering friendliness that provides warmth patients need. Medical students are certainly taught the importance of treating their patients with care, but rarely do they consider their own wellbeing. The health of the world depends on the health of our doctors. The mental health of our physicians has a direct impact on our communities. Through the implementation of programs that emphasize the normalization, acceptance and awareness of mental health issues, medical schools can form a generation of self-healing doctors.

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